

Study of antiferromagnetic interactions of ruthenium(III) ternary complexes

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Manuscript received 1 January 2001, revised 30 July 2001, accepted 15 September 2001

Antiferromagnetic interactions of novel Ru^{III} ternary complexes with α -alanine and nucleic acid constituents, viz. adenine, guanine, cytosine, adenosine, guanosine and cytidine were studied through synthesis and characterization by elemental analysis, IR, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility data.

Transition metal adducts of nucleic acids are studied as probes of nucleic acid structures, as artificial nuclear functions and metallopharmaceuticals¹, and of these Ru^{III} complexes are of current interest as potential anticancer agents². Structure dynamics and energetics of tetrahedral geometric complexes like Pt^{II} adducts are extensively studied, whereas that of Ru^{III} complexes are less known³. In continuation of our studies⁴ on Ru^{III} ternary systems as DNA probes, we herein report the synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of Ru^{III} with α -alanine L(alaH) and nucleic acid constituents, viz. adenine (ade), guanine (gua), cytosine (cyt), adenosine (ado), guanosine (guo) and cytidine (cyd).

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium(III) complexes generally exhibit octahedral structure, which undergo facile redox chemistry⁵. Physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical data of complexes*

Complexes	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-Cl}	$\nu_{C=C}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
[Ru ₂ (alaH)(ade)Cl ₆ (H ₂ O)] (1)	610	300, 360	1500	1600	4.20
[Ru(alaH)(ado)(H ₂ O)Cl ₃]2H ₂ O (2)	600	380, 400	1480	1650	1.97
[Ru ₂ (alaH) ₂ (gua)Cl ₆] (3)	620	290, 400	1520	1600	3.60
[Ru ₂ (alaH) ₂ (gua) ₂ Cl ₆] (4)	610	290, 360	1510	1600	3.60
[Ru ₂ (alaH) ₂ (cyt)Cl ₆ (H ₂ O)]5H ₂ O (5)	550	290, 390	1600	1650	3.50
[Ru(alaH) ₂ (cyd) ₂ (CH ₃ OH) ₂]Cl ₃ (6)	570	-	1500	1650	2.10

*All complex showed satisfactory C, H, N results.

Complex 6 is 3 : 1 electrolyte and complexes 1-5 are non-electrolytes. Complexes 2 and 6 are mono-, six-coordinated complexes with paramagnetism corresponding to one unpaired spin. Complexes 1, 3-5 are binuclear chloro-

bridged Ru^{III} dimers with a very slight bimetallic antiferromagnetic interaction as indicated by their magnetic susceptibility data which is slightly less than one unpaired spin per metal ion, indicating antiferromagnetic interaction in the chloro-bridged Ru^{III} centers.

In all the complexes alanine is coordinated through NH₂ group with a free undissociated COOH group as observed in the ligand.

Complex 2 has a meridional arrangement of chlorides whose stretching frequencies were absorbed at 380 and 400 cm⁻¹ as strong bands (Table 1). Complexes 1, 3-5 have both bridged and terminal chlorides. Bridged M-Cl frequency appeared around 290-300 cm⁻¹ as weak band and ternary chlorides around 360-400 cm⁻¹ as a strong band. In complex 2, adenosine is coordinated through N(7) which is indicated by the shift in C=C and C=N stretching frequencies. The NH₂ stretching frequency was absorbed as in ligand, which supports ring nitrogen in coordination. In complex 1, adenine is coordinated through N(3) and N(9) as reported⁶ for [Ru(cyt)₆](ClO₄)₃ and [Ru(cyt)₄(H₂O)(ClO₄)]²⁺. In case of complex 6, cytidine is coordinated through N(3) as reported earlier⁷ for the complexes of Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} with cytosine and methylcytosine. In complexes 3 and 4, guanine and guanosine are coordinated through N(7) which is supported by the change in the C=C and C=N and ring deformation modes as observed earlier.

¹H NMR spectrum of all the complexes was not obtained due to low solubility and paramagnetic nature.

Experimental

Chromatographically pure nucleic acid constituents and RuCl₃.3H₂O were purchased from Sigma. All the solvents were double-distilled. IR spectra were recorded on PE 983 and elemental analyses were done at CSMCRI, Bhavnagar. IR was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometers. Digisun DI 909 conductivity meter was used. Magnetic susceptibility was recorded on Faraday balance.

Note

To 1 mM metal in methanol solution, 1 mM alanine in water and 1 mM adenine/adenosine/guanosine/cytosine/cytidine in water solutions were added. The mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h on a water-bath and then concentrated. Dark brown colored complexes were precipitated by adding ice-cold acetone. The complexes were filtered, washed with ice-cold acetone and dried in vacuum.

To 1 mM metal solution in methanol, 1 mM alanine in water and 1 mM guanine in water solutions were added. The resulting complex was washed with ice-cold acetone and dried under reduced pressure.

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